

Independent Work of Students as a Factor in Increasing the Effectiveness of the Educational Process

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Abstract: The article examines the role of students' independent work, presents their components, considers the features of mental skills, presents the conditions for the effective organization of students' independent work.

Keywords: independent work, students; individual activity; involvement in creative search; awareness self-improvement.

As is well known, the fundamental factors for enhancing the efficiency of the educational process in higher education institutions, along with training highly qualified specialists, include developing students' abilities for successful independent creative activity and adapting to new learning conditions.

It is important to note that the Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing a comprehensive set of measures aimed at integrating modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process of universities. These include the use of interactive teaching methods that foster the development of students' critical thinking and independent learning skills, ultimately ensuring the quality of education.

In addition, students must acquire methods for collecting, storing, processing, and utilizing information to enhance their abilities to make scientifically grounded and independent decisions. The planning of students' independent work is carried out during the implementation phase of State Educational Standards (SES) and educational-methodological complexes for bachelor's programs, as part of the development of self-study programs.

Independent work by students is a key condition for the qualitative training of highly qualified specialists in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in line with the demands of scientific and technological progress. This work is organized in accordance with the modernization of the content of higher education.

In this regard, there is a need to develop a scientific and methodological approach to organizing students' independent work, taking into account the specifics, content, and teaching methods.

Research dissertations have been conducted on this topic, methodological recommendations have been developed, and seminars and conferences have been held.

However, literary sources often present fragmented and sometimes contradictory information regarding the organization of students' independent work. The need for specific guidance in fostering activity and independence during the learning process was emphasized by the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, particularly through his method of "heuristic dialogue." The goals of education and the factors influencing personality development were also reflected in the works of the ancient Greek philosopher Plato [1].

In the teacher's manual "*Problems of Biology Didactics*," B.V. Vsesvyatsky analyzes specific methods of independent work for students studying biology. The author highlights several key points:

- First, the natural inclination of children and adolescents towards active independent work is emphasized.
- Second, through independent work, students develop creative cognitive activity and initiative, while their interest in studying nature significantly increases.
- Third, to achieve the desired results, teachers must prepare students for independent tasks and guide them in completing these tasks.

The manual emphasizes the necessity of combining independent work, observations, and experiments with attentive listening to the teacher's explanations, examining visual aids, watching educational films, studying textbooks, and reading additional literature. This combination enables students to acquire diverse and comprehensive knowledge about the natural world, along with the necessary skills and abilities to understand it.

The author particularly underscores the idea that while students often aim to memorize theoretical concepts merely to demonstrate good knowledge during assessments, during independent work, they begin to realize that this knowledge is essential for solving the tasks they face.

Thus, the author leads us to the conclusion that, when properly organized, independent work stimulates students' attention during lessons, encouraging them to seek answers to their questions in textbooks and supplementary literature. In this way, independent work significantly influences students' attitudes toward theoretical knowledge.

The essence of the above can be summarized as follows: as students gradually master theoretical knowledge, their independent work naturally becomes more profound. It transitions from merely recording external phenomena to identifying their interconnections, causal relationships, and uncovering some simple patterns [2, 176-178].

It is worth noting that while R.M. Mikelson considers independent work to mean "students completing assignments without any assistance but under the teacher's supervision" [3, 35-36], E.Ya. Golant concludes that the essential features of independent work are, first, the presence of a specific educational task consisting of several actions, and second, the possibility of completing the work without the teacher's direct guidance, though with the teacher checking each action [4, 21-22].

From O.A. Nilson's perspective, independent work is a type of educational activity in which students, under the teacher's guidance, carry out individual, group, or collective tasks while applying the necessary intellectual and/or physical effort [5, 116-117].

V.P. Yesipov defines independent work included in the learning process as a type of activity performed without the teacher's direct involvement but on their assignment, within a specially allocated time. During this process, students consciously aim to achieve the task's objective by applying their efforts and presenting the results of their intellectual or physical (or both) actions in some form [6, 129].

Based on the statement that independent work occurs at all stages of a lesson, including

during the introduction of new knowledge, and represents a qualitatively new phenomenon emphasizing the modern focus on the overall development of students, it is essential to adopt the perspective of L.Sh. Levenberg and R. Ibragimov.

They emphasized the importance of ensuring that, during independent work, students rely on their own knowledge and life experience, present their arguments, and refer to various logical operations (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, abstraction, concretization). Additionally, students should demonstrate initiative and creativity. These aspects must be considered when developing the scientific and methodological foundations for enhancing the effectiveness of students' independent work

Based on the study of philosophical, psychological-pedagogical, methodological, and specialized literature, it is necessary to comprehensively examine the current state of the issue under investigation and its reflection in university teaching practices. Additionally, it is important to identify the methodological and theoretical foundations of students' independent work, as established by K.D. Ushinsky and later affirmed in the works of L.Sh. Levenberg and R. Ibragimov. They argued that students' independence forms a solid foundation for any productive learning process, as "independent work is a central means of activating students' cognitive activity" [7, 96-98].

This viewpoint is logical because the educational and developmental significance of independent work is now beyond question. Independent work enables students to enhance their awareness and retention of knowledge during the learning process, develop a deeper and more conscious mastery of skills, and effectively apply acquired knowledge and skills in changing conditions. It also fosters the development of cognitive abilities such as observation, curiosity, logical thinking, and creative activity. Furthermore, it instills a culture of intellectual and physical labor, equipping students to engage effectively in self-education in the future.

In the study of student independence, various levels of its development were identified based on the methods of acquiring information during the learning process and the role of independent work in ensuring students' scientific and theoretical preparation. The data obtained align with the perspective of N.N. Azizkhodzhayeva, who asserts that independent work is an essential teaching method that involves the individual activity of learners in consolidating acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities (8, 38-41).

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the primary conditions for the effective organization of independent work are as follows:

- ✓ The creative and research-oriented nature of independent work,
- ✓ Individualization of assignments for independent work,
- ✓ Methodological guidance in organizing independent work, and
- ✓ Developing a need for independently acquiring knowledge.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that during the process of self-education, students engage in an in-depth acquaintance with the subject, secondary study, analysis, and self-assessment of results. The ultimate goal of pedagogical self-education for students should be their involvement in creative exploration and multifaceted research activities.

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